

Financial Resources Management of Savitribai Phule Pune University in Maharashtra: A Critical Analysis

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Abstract:

A crucial and necessary resource in educational services is money. The most crucial resource is money, which is transformed into actual teaching materials through a budgeting process and method. The amount of funding allocated to education allows the educational systems to effectively deliver quality education.

The supply of enough funding for the general improvement of educational institutions is a very important duty to improve the quality of education. The purpose of the current study is to examine the funding sources for higher education in India. The majority of the study is based on secondary sources. The data is seen as spanning the years 2012–13 to 2015–16. The grants that Savitribai Phule Pune University has received have been examined through the study.

Keywords: Finance, education, quality education, financial sources, grants

Introduction:

Education is the focal point of each development and is assuming the central part in the steadily changing way of life of person. It is a significant area for monetary, social, and social advancement pointed toward fulfilling the necessities, wants and any desires for a general public overall. Concerning this, United Nation Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2010) noticed that schooling as a vital opportunity of decision and activity, enabling them to partake in friendly and political existences of their general public, and outfitting them with the expertise they need to foster their occupation. Training assumes an imperative part in building a country and improves the advancement on the loose by creating labor supply to the nations. Without instruction advancement and development is unimaginable and incomprehensible. The fundamental hotspots for the financing of advanced education in India incorporates government reserves, assets of self administering bodies, educational expenses, gifts, grants, instructive cess, etc.

Accordingly, advanced education is considered as one of the main interest in the long term plans of the public authority and among the public level speculations for the improvement of the human culture. However, it is vital to use those monetary assets monetarily and sensibly for come by the normal outcomes from the advanced education area and make it the most splendid

one among the advanced education frameworks of the world.

Higher education in India:

It remained exceptionally internal arranged in spite of a few post-freedom changes in schooling area. As far as number of instructive establishments, India has the world's biggest advanced education framework with around 1,000 colleges and 40,000 universities though it positions third as far as size and variety, however its quality in the worldwide training framework has been horrifyingly beneath its actual potential that stays neglected. India's advanced education framework is the world's third-biggest as far as understudies, close to China and the United States. India's Higher Education area has seen an enormous expansion in the quantity of Universities/University level Institutions and Colleges since autonomy. In the prestigious Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) World University Rankings 2020, only three Indian Universities- IIT-Bombay, IIT-Delhi and IISc (Bangalore)- have been included in the top 200 institutes.

Educational Finance:

Instructive money remembers the idea of speculation for man and its effect lies upon the cycles which are worried about the monetary advancement of the country. Whenever training is considered as a course of interest in more youthful age of the general public, this additionally prompts the satisfaction of future requests expected by the general public from its speculation.

Subsequently, every general public has an assumption for exceptional yields from its use on human and material assets. This course of use on schooling can be perceived as a course of renouncing of present happiness for having an expansion in the progression of profits later on. Thus, we can think about instructive money as a cycle that comprises of pay, use and saving a harmony between the two for the advantage if the general public.

It is said that instructive money is expected to fill various needs prefer to set out new instructive open doors, to keep up with the ordinary instructive administrations, to grow the current instructive offices, to extend the instructive administrations, to diminish in differences in the instructive open doors, to increment in the quantitative parts of training, to increment in the nature of schooling.

Significance of the study:

Advanced education is one of the main pieces of the training framework through which it is relied upon to make learned and useful residents for a country. For the smooth working and quality result from the higher instructive establishments, instructive money is the main component. Subsequently, it is vital to comprehend the course of money in advanced education so we can find out with regards to the consumption on training and potential returns that we can get from that speculation which will signify the accomplishment of the entire advanced education framework.

Objectives of the study:

- To study the different sources of finance in higher education
- To study the grants received by Savitribai Phule Pune University

Hypothesis of the study:

H0: There is no significance difference in grants received by Savitribai Phule Pune University

Savitribai Phule Pune University:

Savitribai Phule Pune University, formerly University of Pune and University of Poona, is a university in Pune in western India, founded in 10 February 1949. Spread over a 411 acres (1.66 km²) campus, the university is home to 43 academic departments. The university is named after Savitribai Phule, a 19th-century Indian social reformer who is known for her contribution towards empowerment and

emancipation of women through education. The university has affiliated colleges, departments, and research institutes, which are primarily in Pune.

Sources of Finance in Higher Education:

RashtriyaUchchatarShikshaAbhiyan:(R USA) RashtriyaUchchatar Shiksha Abhiyan, a centrally sponsored scheme (CSS), launched in 2013 aims at providing strategic funding to eligible state higher educational institutions. RUSA is envisaged as the prime vehicle for strategic funding of state institutions so as to ensure that issues of access, equity and quality are addressed in an equitable manner. All funding under RUSA are norm based and future grants would be performance based and outcome dependent.

Governmental bodies: In India, education is included in the concurrent list i.e. education is considered as the joint responsibility of both center and the state. The government funds are created and distributed through its various agencies like UGC, NCERT, NCTE, NUEPA, AICTE, SCERT etc. The central government of India has been framing several policies and schemes and the state government is required to implement those in every now and then. Apart from that both the central and state government jointly frame enormous schemes to uplift the financial provisions of the students in the form of scholarships, fellowships etc.

Local bodies: In managing education, local bodies also furnish as an important means of financial help whenever necessary. Different local bodies like Zila Parishad, Panchayat Samities, Nagar Panchayats, Gram Panchayats, Municipalities and Corporations etc. are working for the fulfilment of educational goals in the higher educational institutions at the grass root level. **Private funds:** Private assets signifies the assets which are designated through the gifts, memberships, gifts, estates, fines, deal continues, premium on bank adjusts, lease from structures and so forth. These are additionally called public altruism. Private assets for the higher instructive establishments additionally incorporate those foundations which are controlled by the private bodies and subsequently reserves are created through their own pay amassed from different sources.

Grant-in-aid: Grants are given by the public authority or through its different offices to the higher instructive establishments. The monetary assistance or commitment as cash or material merchandise by a greater government to a more modest unit of it is known as an award. These awards might be given a periodical installment or once premise by zeroing in on a particular region under the heads like ordered award, compensatory award, different awards, the debatable and hoc award and so on.

Fees: The fees are collected from the students in return of the tuition or other services provided to them in the educational institution. Fees generally includes admission fees, tuition fees, library fees, examination fees, fees collected for co-curricular activities, laboratory fees, electricity fees etc.

Endowment and land grant: Strict foundations and different associations or NGO's keep to the side a few piece of their gathered cash or pay to spend in instruction and these associations give this measure of cash for the government assistance of instructive organizations and consequently the enriched universities or instructive

Grants received by university:

Following is the data of grants received by Savitribai Phule Pune University from 2012-13 to 2015-16.

Grants/Year	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16
State	1409.64	158.42	251.24	237.48
UGC	2333.12	1729.66	1191.6	1460.7
CSIR	155.01	131.25	138.07	135.32
GOI	2675.90	1024.69	1271.48	2229.95
OIB	86.34	132.36	197.87	173.3
Grand Total	6660.01	3176.38	3050.26	4236.75

Above table shows the grants received by Savitribai Phule Pune University from 2012-13 to 2015-16. From the table it is observed that State grant is continuously declining. It was 1409.64 in the year of 2012-13 and in 2015-16 it decreased to 237.78. Also the UGC, CSIR, GOI funding is declining only OIB grant is increasing in constant rate. The overall grant from 2012-13 to 2015-16 also declining.

Graphical presentation of grants received by Savitribai Phule Pune University:

establishments get profited from such gifts. Enrichment reserves, gifts, gifts and other such kind of willful commitments from people or firms, manufacturing plants, sanctuaries, temples and so on are remembered for the pay from blessings for the instructive foundations.

Other Sources of income: The higher educational institutions also generate income from donations, gifts, subscriptions, fines, money from rents, loans, debts. etc. and all these are included in the other sources of income

Income from Alumni Fund: Pay from the graduated class can be of one more conceivable elective kind of revenue for the colleges. Clark (2003, p. 104) determines that pay acquired from graduated class raising money, reserved for long haul general help or to be spent in the present time and place, is a top notch source. Consequently, the college can lay out a decent contact with the graduated class for raising a few assets. Consequently, from all the previously mentioned sources the higher instructive foundations are creating pay for the satisfaction of its various purposes.

(Plotted from above table)

Hypothesis Testing:

The hypotheses refers to the basic statements formulated for their confirmation in analysis done in the various chapters of the study, these are the outcomes set before the study

for the conclusion. Students t test have been used for this study.

H0: There is no significance difference in grants received by Savitrbai Phule Pune University

Students t test analysis of grants received by Savitrbai Phule Pune University

Variable	Value
Average	4280.85
Standard Deviation	1672.98
t-value	3.41
p Value	0.0135

The above table provides the description of grants received by Savitrbai Phule Pune University from 2013 to 2026. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 we have sufficient evidence to reject null hypothesis at 5% significance level. So we can reject null hypothesis.

Conclusion: There is significant difference in grants received by Savitrbai Phule Pune University.

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